

Does Halal Tourism Policy Attract More Tourists? Evidence from Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The Government of Indonesia has implemented halal tourism strategies to attract tourists from Muslim countries since 2013. The number of tourist arrivals from Muslim countries has been growing since then, and so has that of non-Muslim countries. This study uses an augmented gravity model for bilateral tourism flows to examine the effect of halal tourism policy on the number of tourist arrivals in Indonesia. The results provide statistical evidence that halal tourism policy is effective and quite powerful in attracting foreign tourist arrivals. It increases tourist arrivals from both Muslim and non-Muslim countries by 21%. Furthermore, our findings suggest important implication for policy makers in designing tourism strategies.

ملخص

نفذت حكومة إندونيسيا استراتيجيات للسياحة الحلال لجذب السياح من البلدان الإسلامية منذ عام 2013. ويتزايد عدد السياح الوافدين من البلدان الإسلامية منذ ذلك الحين، وكذلك من الدول غير الإسلامية. وتستخدم هذه الدراسة نموذج الجاذبية المعززة لتدفقات السياحة الثنائية لدراسة تأثير سياسة السياحة الحلال على عدد السياح الوافدين إلى إندونيسيا. وتقدم النتائج دليلاً إحصائياً على أن سياسة السياحة الحلال فعالة وقوية للغاية في جذب السياح الأجانب الوافدين. وتساهم في زيادة عدد السياح الوافدين من الدول الإسلامية وغير الإسلامية بنسبة 21%. وعلاوة على ذلك، تشير النتائج التي توصلنا إليها إلى بعض التأثيرات المهمة التي يمكن لصناع السياسات الاحتذاء بها في تصميم استراتيجيات السياحة.

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ABSTRAITE

Le gouvernement indonésien a mis en œuvre des stratégies de tourisme halal pour attirer les touristes des pays musulmans depuis 2013. Le nombre d'arrivée de touristes en provenance de pays musulmans a augmenté depuis lors, tout comme celui des pays non musulmans. Cette étude utilise un modèle de gravité augmenté pour les flux touristiques bilatéraux afin d'examiner l'effet de la politique de tourisme halal sur le nombre d'arrivée de touristes en Indonésie. Les résultats fournissent des preuves statistiques que la politique de tourisme halal est efficace et assez puissante pour attirer les arrivées de touristes étrangers. Elle augmente de 19% les arrivées de touristes en provenance de pays musulmans et non-musulmans. En outre, nos résultats suggèrent des implications importantes pour les décideurs politiques dans la conception de stratégies touristiques.

Keywords: gravity model, religion, tourist arrivals, halal tourism, Indonesia

JEL Classification: L83, Z32, Z12

1. Introduction

Brand image represents a key element in branding products and services. Tourist destination branding is one way to promote tourism destinations and increase the competitiveness (Huang et al., 2013). However, designing a strong brand quality has been a particular concern nowadays due to an intense competition among tourist destinations. For several tourist destinations, religious and spiritual motivations have become popular brands. These motivations have occupied an important position in international tourism and have grown rapidly in recent years.

Religion has played a fairly important role in the development of travel over the centuries and has influenced the way people spend their free time. The influence of religion on decision making has been emphasised a lot in the consumer behaviour literature (Williams 2002; Arnold et al. 2004). Religion is equally important when it comes to symbolic expression and identity construction in consumer behaviour (Arnold et al., 2004). Williams (2002) analysed the importance of religion as a subculture that influences consumption of hotel and hospitality services. It is because the role of religion on tourism is associated with the conceptualisation of cultural affinity in the decision-making process.

For Muslim tourists, their religion will govern daily decisions when traveling (Jafari and Scott, 2014; Stephenson, 2014; Devi & Firmansyah, 2019). It is different from the western tourism concept which allows hedonic tourism activities such as alcohol consumption and gambling which are against Islamic principles (Zamani-Farahani & Henderson, 2010). There is a lot of literature explaining that Muslim tourists are more likely to visit destinations that are thick with Islamic attributes (Battour et al., 2011; Nassar et al., 2015). However, their studies failed to investigate whether religion influences the decision-making process for tourists to Islamic destinations.

As a country with religious and cultural diversity, Indonesia has historical and traditional heritage that cannot be separated from religious aspect. Cultural and religious heritage with a diversity of races, ethnicities, languages and customs become a potential tourism development in Indonesia. As the majority of the population in Indonesia, Muslims certainly have a uniqueness that characterizes the nation with existing tourist destinations, such as palaces, mosques, heirlooms, tombs, and the associated culinary delights (Jaelani et al., 2016). This polarization of culture and religious practices of Muslims has attracted tourists to visit Indonesia.

In order to serve the growing interest of Muslim tourists, particularly from Muslim populated countries in Middle East, the Indonesian Ministry of Trade has taken a formal strategy to develop the halal segment in tourism industry since 2012. It includes the implementation of hotel classification requirements, which serves only food based on halal dietary and prohibits alcohol drinks, and the enactment of preliminary growth targets for Muslim arrivals. The Government of Indonesia subsequently continued their strategy by designating 12 provinces as Muslim-friendly destination, including Aceh, West Sumatra, Riau, Lampung, Banten, Jakarta, West Java, Central Java, Yogyakarta, East Java, West Nusa Tenggara and South Sulawesi in 2013. This effort has attracted potential investors to support the halal segment in tourism industry and brought positive outcomes to Indonesia as the country has successfully obtained three awards in the 2015 World Halal Tourism: the 1st World's Best Halal Honeymoon Destination, the 1st World's Best Halal Tourism Destination, and the 1st World's Best Family Friendly Hotel.

The number of inbound tourists from Muslim countries in Indonesia seems to increase throughout the years, and so is that from non-Muslim countries, particularly after the introduction of halal tourism policy in 2013 (See Figure 1). The aim of this study is then to examine whether the government strategy in halal tourism contributes effectively to attract tourist arrivals in Indonesia, especially from Muslim countries since they are the main target of halal tourism policy. Positive effect in halal tourism policy would indicate the need for and importance of accommodating and strengthening Muslim-friendly tourism initiatives for the development of Indonesia's tourism industry.

Figure 1: Tourist Arrivals in Indonesia, 2006-2019

Source: Statistics Indonesia

This study uses an augmented gravity model for bilateral tourism flows to estimate the impact of the government's halal tourism strategy on the number of inbound tourists. Following Ghani (2016), we use a country's membership in the Organisation of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) to proxy for Muslim countries since membership in OIC often reflects formal or informal state religion within the country. This research is expected to offer a novel contribution to the existing literature of gravity model in tourism given that it is the first attempt to consider the role of halal tourism policy in the context of Indonesia as the largest Muslim country in the world.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Religion and Tourism

Many facets of life may be affected by religious beliefs. Thus, it is possible to assert that these beliefs may also shape tourists' decision to travel. An extensive literature promotes the view that religion is a pull factor for tourists (Hyde & Harman, 2011; della Dora, 2012). Religion may affect tourism in two different ways. First, religion may deter tourist arrivals through explicit policies that prevent tourists with different beliefs from the dominant religion and religious identity of the destination country, such as the presence of ultraconservative believers (Cohen, 1998). For example, different attitudes of non-Muslim tourists from prevailing Islamic cultural values and local traditions have led to the resistance of Muslim communities in the destination countries (Haija, 2011). Therefore, in several Muslim countries such as Brunei and Saudi Arabia, tourism is not the leading sector in country's development (Zamani-Farahani & Henderson, 2010).

Second, religion motivates tourism through religious affinity and cultural interests from shared values and beliefs (Balaam & Dillman, 2015). Religion is a cultural trait that influences tourists' selection of their destination. Even, when a trip is not driven by religious purpose, it still has indirect effect on tourism since tourists are often manifested to religion on their travels (Stausberg, 2011). The similarity of dominant religion of a destination to theirs could be an important determinant of their choice of destination. Vietze (2012) examines the effect of religion on tourist arrivals in the United States. His results reveal that sharing religious similarity has a positive impact on bilateral tourism flows after controlling for economic, geographic, cultural and political variables. Furthermore, Fourie et al. (2015) investigate whether sharing a common major religion determines global tourism flows. They find that sharing the same dominant religion has a positive effect on tourism flows. This indicates that tourists tend to visit countries with religious similarity as their own, especially Hinduism and Islam.

Fundamentally, Islam itself does not oppose tourism. The Qur'an even encourages Muslims to travel to gain knowledge, to mingle with other Muslims, and to enjoy and appreciate Allah's creation. However, religion still obligates Muslim to maintain their religious practices, consume halal

products and keep following the rules of the Islamic Religion during their travel. Thus, this calls for awareness from tourism service providers to satisfy the needs of Muslim tourists, especially those related to religious practices. Provisions of religious facilities and halal products in tourist destination countries would make Muslim tourists more comfortable during their trips.

Furthermore, many countries are encouraged to start implementing Muslim-friendly or halal tourism policies in order to attract more Muslim tourists, with no exceptions of Indonesia. This does not necessarily mean that halal tourism products and services are exclusive and promoted only to Muslim tourists (El-Gohary, 2016). The introduction of halal tourism even would attract more opportunities for cultural and marketing exchanges between Muslim and non-Islamic communities (Wilson et al., 2013). This is particularly relevant for tourists from non-Muslim countries by exposing them to a new experience with different cultures and relieving the fear associated with negative media portrayal of Muslim countries after the 9/11 incident (Ghani, 2019).

2.2. Tourism Sector and Economic Development in Indonesia

Tourism sector has become one of the sectors that contributes greatly to the foreign exchange earnings in the Indonesian economy. The contribution of the tourism sector to the country's foreign exchange has reached USD 11 billion in 2016 and kept rising until 2018, reaching up to USD 16 billion.³ This is equivalent to 11.26% of country's foreign exchange. Tourism sector also has consistently made a positive contribution to Indonesia's services trade balance in terms of services export. Nonetheless, the contribution of the tourism sector to Indonesia's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) appeared to be stagnant, which is around 4% in the latest five years.⁴

The development of tourism is closely related to economic development. In general, tourism can help eliminate economic disparities in various countries (Mowforth & Munt, 2009). Tourism can also help a country to achieve the Millennium Development Goals, alleviate poverty, create jobs and empower women (Hawkins & Mann, 2007). In the case of Indonesia, without tourism activities, Indonesia's poverty rate will be 4%

³ Central Bureau of Statistics Indonesia, 2020.

⁴ Central Bureau of Statistics Indonesia, 2018.

higher in 2014-2016 (Riyanto et al, 2020). Any increase in tourism activities would encourage investment in various sectors such as transportation, accommodations, services, food and beverages, which consequently has a positive impact on employment and economic growth in Indonesia.

2.2.1. Tourist arrivals to Indonesia from Muslim and non-Muslim countries

Table 1 presents the top five tourist arrivals in Indonesia by country of origin in 2019. It can be seen that most tourist arrivals in Indonesia come from non-Muslim countries rather than Muslim countries. In total, there were around 3.2 million of tourist arrivals from Muslim countries, which was only one third of those from non-Muslim countries. The contribution of tourist arrivals from Muslim countries amounted up to 25% of total inbound tourists. Malaysia and Saudi Arabia are the top two Muslim countries of foreign tourist arrivals in Indonesia, whilst China and Singapore are the two largest tourist origin countries from non-Muslim countries. The contribution of tourists from China and Singapore to total inbound tourists is even greater than that of all tourists from Muslim countries.

Table 1: Top Five Tourist Arrivals in Indonesia by Country, 2019

OIC-Countries			Non-OIC		
Malaysia	2,980,753	22.63%	China	2,072,079	15.73%
Saudi Arabia	157,512	1.20%	Singapore	1,934,445	14.69%
Egypt	21,354	0.16%	Australia	1,386,803	10.53%
Brunei Darussalam	19,278	0.15%	India	657,3	4.99%
Pakistan	14,663	0.11%	Japan	519,623	3.94%
Total	3,222,228	24.47%	Total	9,949,789	75.53%

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics Indonesia

2.2.2. Initiatives to attract Muslim tourists

The Indonesian government is quite serious in developing tourism sector. This can be seen from their commitment of signing a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) between the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy and the National Sharia Council to make Indonesia a leading

destination for world Islamic tourism. The government also has been aggressively promoting Indonesia as a Muslim travel destination by producing some brochures that spotlight the best tourism destinations in the country based on Islamic tourism viewpoint. The brochures also mention that there are more than 600,000 mosques in the country.

The Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy has taken another step by assigning a special committee named the ‘Team for the Acceleration of Halal Tourism Development’ to help overcome some coordination issues in the development of halal tourism sector. The team has selected three provinces to heavily invest in that development of Islamic tourism. One of them is West Nusa Tenggara, with particular emphasis on Lombok Island. So far, there have been nine hotels in Lombok Island promoting themselves as Islamic hotels with halal certification. To be halal-certified, hotels are required to have signs pointing toward Qibla, provide Qur’an in their room and a kitchen where halal food can be prepared .

The Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy has also collaborated with the National Sharia Council and the Business Certification Institute to develop the tourism potential and maintain standards of Islamic values for the development of Islamic tourism industry. Since 2013, the Jakarta Culture and Tourism Office and the National Sharia Council altogether have created Halal certificates for hotels, restaurants and caterers in the capital city as a concrete way to attract more Muslim tourists. The certification was even provided free to Small Micro and Medium Enterprises that produce foods and drinks with management training in Halal production.

The efforts of Indonesian government to make Indonesia a global destination have yielded results both in terms of the number of tourist arrivals and the awards of which Indonesia has won. For example, Indonesia has won 12 awards from 16 contested categories from beach resorts to airlines in the 2016 World Halal Tourism Awards competition held in Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates.

3. Method

In this study, we use an augmented gravity model to examine the effect of implementation of halal tourism policy on tourist arrivals to Indonesia. The gravity model is based on Newton’s law of gravity and has been

extensively used as an empirical tool to explain trade and other economic flows, see Gupta et al. (2019). In recent years, the gravity models have been repetitively employed to explain the bilateral tourism flows. It was started from Rodrigue (2004), who has adjusted the gravity model introduced by Tinbergen (1962), so that the model is applicable in the tourism area. This model is widely used in the most rigorous studies in tourism literature given that the number of tourist arrivals in the country depends on particular characteristics of the origin countries and the destination (Adeola & Evans, 2019).

In the present study, we apply panel data technique of country-pair variables given that it offers a higher prospect of identifying the primary determinants of tourism arrivals (Fourie et al., 2015). We derive a gravity model based on the consumer choice theory (Morley et al., 2014). The specification of the model can be written as follows.

$$\ln(\text{Tourist arrival})_{ijt} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{halal policy})_{jt} + \beta_2 \ln(\text{Distance})_{ij} + \beta_3 \ln(\text{GDP per capita})_{jt} + \beta_4 \ln(\text{Population})_{jt} + \beta_5(\text{Political stability})_{it} + \beta_6(\text{Political stability})_{jt} + \beta_7 \ln(\text{Exchange rate})_{ijt} + \beta_8(\text{Temperature difference})_{ijt} + \varepsilon_{ijt}, \quad (1)$$

where \ln denotes natural logs; i and j refer to the host country, which is Indonesia, and origin countries, respectively, and t is time. β_0 is the constant term, β_n are the parameters to estimate of each variable taken into account, while ε_{ijt} is the error term. The logarithmic specification allows the interpretation of the parameters of estimation as elasticities and reduces the magnitude differences of the variables.

The dependent variable is $\ln(\text{Tourist arrival})$, or the natural log of the number of tourist arrivals in Indonesia. Halal policy is a dummy indicating year of implementation of government strategy in halal tourism. We assign 1 for year 2013 onwards to represent the government strategy of enacting 12 Muslim friendly destinations, while 0 for any periods prior to 2013. Traditional gravity variables include the natural log of origin's real gross domestic product per capita, $\ln(\text{GDP per capita})$, to measure the purchasing power of tourists, and the natural log of geographical distance between capital cities in kilometers, $\ln(\text{Distance})$, to proxy for transport costs. A set of bilateral controls are added, such as the natural log of population, $\ln(\text{population})$, to measure the size of origin countries and the natural log of nominal bilateral exchange, $\ln(\text{exchange rate})$, as a proxy for destination prices. Moreover, country-specific

variables such as the temperature difference, the level of political stability and absence of violence/terrorism in the origin countries and the destination are included.

Due to the availability of the data, the dataset only covers 36 major countries of origin from 2006 to 2019 (See Table 2 for further details). The data used in this study are retrieved from Statistics Indonesia, the World Bank, the OIC and the *Centre de recherche français dans le domaine de l'économie internationale* (CEPII). Since we use panel data, we are able to control the heterogeneity among countries. Then, we estimate our empirical model (1) using three basic methods in the panel data approach, namely ordinary least squares (OLS), fixed effects and random effects model. The fixed effect model assumes that each country has country-specific variables that are not observed on its own and estimates separate constants for each country. Meanwhile, the random-effects model assumes country-specific variables that do not follow normal distribution and constant throughout the estimated periods.

Table 2: The Origin Countries of Tourist

Brunei Darussalam	India	China	Sweden	Qatar	Egypt
Malaysia	Japan	Australia	Portugal	Yemen	Finland
Philippines	South Korea	New Zealand	Spain	France	Switzerland
Singapore	Pakistan	USA	Netherland	Bahrain	United Kingdom
Thailand	Denmark	Canada	Italy	Saudi Arabia	Russia
Kuwait	Sri Lanka	Austria	Germany	Arab Emirates	Belgium

4. Result and Discussion

Table 3 presents the results from OLS, fixed effects and random effects. The results obtained by the three procedures are quite similar, while fixed effects model is selected among the three after a series of tests (Breusch-Pagan LM test and Hausman test). In general, the coefficients of explanatory variables behave as expected. The population of origin countries has significantly positive effects on tourist arrivals, implying that larger countries send more tourists to Indonesia. Economic and institutional factors such as GDP per capita of origin country, bilateral

exchange rate and political stability of the destination country are correlated with tourist arrivals, indicating the importance of such factors in affecting tourist arrivals.

Table 3: Panel Data Estimations for Full Sample

Dependent Variable: ln(tourist arrivals)	OLS	Fixed effects	Random Effects
Halal policy	0.216* (0.126)	0.241*** (0.043)	0.219*** (0.044)
ln(distance)	-1.507*** (0.073)	1.314 (1.466)	-1.256*** (0.268)
ln(GDP per capita)	0.067 (0.052)	0.945*** (0.140)	0.451*** (0.098)
ln(population)	0.894*** (0.031)	1.015*** (0.192)	0.700*** (0.093)
Political stability of origin	0.798*** (0.082)	-0.062 (0.060)	0.065 (0.059)
Political stability of destination	0.574*** (0.208)	0.476*** (0.070)	0.499*** (0.067)
ln(exchange rate)	0.192*** (0.051)	-0.174* (0.105)	0.265*** (0.078)
Temperature difference	0.028*** (0.006)	-0.012 (0.029)	0.031* (0.017)
Constants	6.405*** (1.226)	-28.360 (11.186)	2.699 (3.086)
R-square	0.750	0.978	0.627
Observations	504	504	504
Hausman test (chi2)		38.16***	
Breusch-Pagan LM test (chibar2)		2446.56***	

Notes: ***, ** and * are significant at 1%, 5% and 10% levels, respectively. Standard errors are in parentheses.

The estimated elasticity of tourist arrivals with respect to the GDP per capita of the tourists' country of origin is around 0.95, indicating that tourism demand in Indonesia is income inelastic. A 1% increase in income would lead to an increase in tourist arrivals of less than 1%. The estimated elasticity measure of income is quite similar with the estimates produced by gravity model studies that use tourist arrivals as the dependent variable, for example Ghani (2016). Negative effects of bilateral exchange rate indicate that currency appreciation in the destination country reduces tourist arrivals since the price level is relatively more expensive than the origin country. Finally, political stability and absence of violence or terrorism in the destination country seems to have positive effect on

tourist arrivals. This implies that more stable political situation in the destination country will attract more foreign tourists to visit.

Regarding the main variable of interest, results suggest that halal tourism policy has a positive effect on tourist arrivals. The effect is around 24%, indicating a substantial increase in foreign tourist arrivals after the implementation of halal tourism strategies. This finding implies that the introduced halal tourism initiatives have benefited Indonesia in general.

For further analysis, we disaggregate our data into Muslim countries and non-Muslim countries to check whether there is any change in magnitude of the policy effect on tourist arrivals. Table 4 summarizes our results. Economic and institutional factors seem to remain qualitatively similar with the estimates in full sample for both Muslim and non-Muslim countries. Estimates from fixed effects model reveal that halal tourism policy increases tourist arrivals from Muslim countries by 21.8%. This result may indicate that tourists from Muslim countries tend to visit countries with similar religious affiliation to their own and halal tourism policy in Indonesia makes it easier to implement halal lifestyle during their trips.

Interestingly, the halal tourism strategies also appear to attract tourists from non-Muslim countries. As the coefficients of halal policy suggest, the government strategy in halal tourism can attract more tourists from non-Muslim countries around 21.4% based on random effects model. In contrast to Fourie et al. (2015) who find that Muslim destinations do not attract many tourists from different religions, our finding may indicate a growing interest from people in non-Muslim countries toward halal tourism. Battour et al. (2018) reveal in their studies that overall perception of tourists from non-Muslim countries toward halal tourism is moderately positive. Majority of their respondents have travelled to Muslim countries to learn and try Muslim culture. They even enjoyed safer environment offered by Muslim countries. The findings in our study then provides statistical evidence that halal tourism strategy may successfully attract tourists from non-Muslim countries who are interested to Muslim culture and halal lifestyle.

Table 4: Panel Data Estimations by OIC membership

Dependent Variable: ln(tourist arrivals)	Non-Muslim countries			Muslim countries		
	OLS	Fixed Effects	Random Effects	OLS	Fixed Effects	Random Effects
Halal policy	0.063 (0.241)	0.266** (0.111)	0.214** (0.109)	0.172* (0.100)	0.218*** (0.041)	0.193*** (0.042)
ln(distance)	-2.059*** (0.183)	-31.230 (24.197)	-1.653 (0.568)	-1.649*** (0.080)	-0.040 (0.566)	-1.392*** (0.292)
ln(GDP per capita)	-0.539*** (0.139)	0.281 (0.302)	0.228 (0.257)	0.340*** (0.047)	1.303*** (0.162)	0.587*** (0.091)
ln(population)	1.540*** (0.090)	0.377 (0.388)	0.468** (0.231)	0.817*** (0.029)	1.062** (0.525)	0.662*** (0.093)
Political stability of origin	0.562*** (0.204)	0.001 (0.156)	0.037 (0.156)	0.760*** (0.072)	-0.065 (0.057)	0.107* (0.055)
Political stability of destination	0.732* (0.402)	0.884*** (0.210)	0.867*** (0.186)	0.398** (0.166)	0.332*** (0.064)	0.371*** (0.063)
ln(exchange rate)	-0.066 (0.087)	-0.579** (0.225)	-0.327* (0.188)	0.449*** (0.047)	0.067 (0.115)	0.537*** (0.081)
Temperature difference	-0.597*** (0.085)	-0.132 (0.123)	-0.134 (0.114)	-0.003 (0.005)	0.011 (0.025)	0.003 (0.016)
Constants	9.176*** (1.870)	282.045 (211.914)	16.564 (6.549)	4.273 (1.259)	-22.96*** (6.652)	1.287 (3.304)
R-square	0.800	0.967	0.476	0.791	0.976	0.693
Observations	140	140	140	364	364	364
Hausman test (chi2)		11.02			40.61***	
Breusch-Pagan LM test (chibar2)		477.16***			1532.53***	

5. Conclusion

As the largest Muslim country in the world, the Government of Indonesia has taken several strategies to develop the halal segment in tourism industry to attract tourists from Muslim countries. The strategies include certification for halal hotel and designation of 12 provinces as Muslim-friendly destination. Although the number of tourist arrivals from Muslim countries keep increasing, it is still fewer than that of non-Muslim countries. These motivate this study to evaluate the effectiveness of halal tourism policy in attracting tourists from overseas, especially from Muslim countries.

Using a gravity model framework for bilateral tourism flows, this study finds that the government strategy in halal tourism is effective as it can

attract tourist arrivals to Indonesia up to 24%. This effect is observable in Muslim countries and even non-Muslim countries hence the policy has benefited Indonesia in general. Therefore, we can recommend that halal tourism should be strengthened and promoted further given that it does not deter tourists from non-Muslim countries to visit a country with Muslim-friendly environment. In addition to current strategies in halal tourism, the tourism agency could offer special tour packages for tourists coming to Muslim-friendly destination in the country.

However, it is worth mentioning that the database used in the study is limited to several countries with complete data support research question. To better understand the experience and satisfaction of foreign tourists with respect to halal tourism, future research should use more detailed survey with micro-data at the country level.

References

- Adeola, O. & Evans, O. (2019). Digital Tourism: Mobile Phones, Internet and Tourism in Africa. *Tourism Recreation Research*, 44(2), 190-202.
- Arnold, E., Price, L. & Zinkhan, G. (2004). Consumers. New York: McGraw-Hill
- Balaam, D.N. & Dillman, B. (2015). Introduction to international political economy. Routledge.
- Battour, M., Ismail, M. & Battor, M. (2011). The Impact of Destination Attributes on Muslim Tourist's Choice. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 13(6), 527– 540.
- Battour, M., Hakimian, F., Ismail, M. & Bogan, E. (2018). The Perception of non-Muslim Tourist towards Halal Tourism: Evidence from Turkey and Malaysia. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 9(4), 823-840.
- Cohen, E. (1998). Tourism and religion: a comparative perspective. *Pacific Tourism Review*, 2(1), 1–10.
- della Dora, V. (2012). Setting and Blurring Boundaries: Pilgrims, Tourists, and Landscape in Mount Athos and Meteora. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 39, 951–974.
- Devi, A. & Firmansyah, I. (2019). Developing Halal Travel and Halal Tourism to Promote Economic Growth: A Confirmatory Analysis. *Journal Of Islamic Monetary Economics and Finance*, 5(1), 193-214.
- El-Gohary, H. (2016). Halal tourism, is it really Halal? *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 19(B), 124-130.
- Fourie, J., Rossello, J. & Santana-Gallego, M. (2015). Religion, Religious Diversity and Tourism. *Kyklos*, 68(1), 51-64.
- Ghani, G. M. (2016). Tourist Arrivals to Malaysia from Muslim Countries. *Tourism Management Perspectives*. 20, 1-9.
- Ghani, G. M. (2019). Tourist Arrivals to Muslim Countries: Pre- and Post-September 11. *Journal of Economic Cooperation and Development*. 40(3), 25-36.

- Gupta, R., Gozgor, G., Kaya, H. & Demir, E. (2019). Effects of geopolitical risks on trade flows: evidence from the gravity model. *Eurasian Economic Review*, 9, 515–530.
- Haija, A. A. (2011). Jordan: Tourism and conflict with local communities. *Habitat International*, 35(1), 93–100.
- Hawkins, D. & Mann, S. (2007). The World Bank's Role in Tourism Development. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 34(2), 348–363.
- Huang, C., Oh, K., Zhang, Q. & Choi, Y.J. (2013). Understanding the City Brand in the Regional Tourism Market Among College Students. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 30, 662–671.
- Hyde, K.F. & Harman, S. (2011). Motives for a secular pilgrimage to the Gallipoli battle fields. *Tourism Management*. 32, 1343–1351.
- Jaelani, A., Setyawan, E. & Hasyim, N. (2016), Religious Heritage Tourism and Creative Economy in Cirebon: The Diversity of Religious, Cultures and Culinary. *Journal of Social and Administrative Sciences*, 3(1), 63-76.
- Jafari, J. & Scott, N. (2014). Muslim World and its Tourisms. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 44, 1–19.
- Mowforth, M. & Munt, I. (2009). *Tourism and Sustainability: Development, Globalisation and New Tourism in the Third World*. Routledge.
- Morley, C., Rosselló, J. & Santana-Gallego, M. (2014). Gravity Models for Tourism Demand: Theory and Use. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 48: 1–10.
- Nassar, M., Mostafa, M. & Reisinger, Y. (2015). Factors Influencing Travel to Islamic Destinations: An Empirical Analysis of Kuwaiti Nationals. *International Journal of Culture, Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 9(1), 36–53.
- Rodrigue, J. P. (2004). *The Geography of Transport Heights*. World Travel and Tourism Council. London: Routledge
- Riyanto, Massie, N.W.G, Hartono, D, Revindo, M.D, Usman, Riyadi, S.A, Puspita, N. & Wikarya, U. (2020). The Impact of Tourism on Poverty Alleviation and Income Distribution: Evidence from Indonesia. LPEM-FEBUI Working Paper-047. 1-13.

- Stausberg, M. (2011). *Religion and tourism: crossroads, destinations and encounters*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Stephenson, M. (2014). Deciphering “Islamic Hospitality”: Developments, Challenges and Opportunities. *Tourism Management*, 40, 155–164.
- Tinbergen. (1962). An Analysis of World Trade Flows in Shaping the *World Economy*, 5(1), 27-30.
- Vietze, C. (2012). Cultural effects on inbound tourism into the USA: A gravity approach. *Tourism Economics*. 18, 121–138.
- Williams, A. (2002). *Understanding the Hospitality Consumer*. Butterworth-Heinemann, Oxford.
- Wilson, J.A., Belk, R.W., Bamossy, G.J., Sandikci, Ö., Kartajaya, H., Sobh, R., Liu, J. & Scott, L. (2013). Crescent marketing, Muslim geographies and brand Islam: reflections from the JIMA Senior Advisory Board. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 4(1), 22-50.
- Zamani-Farahani, H. & Henderson, J.C. (2010). Islamic Tourism and Managing Tourism Development in Islamic Societies: The Cases of Iran and Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Tourist Research*, 12(1), 79–89.